

IMPLEMENTATION OF BASIC AIOT SYSTEM

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Abstract. *IoT (Internet of Things) technology and AI technology are representative technologies of the 4th industrial revolution era. Each technology is being developed and researched in different ways, but the cooperation between the two technologies is very important. In this study, we implemented a device that measures the external environment temperature, analyzes the measured data on a computer, and displays the results on the computer's monitoring screen. We added artificial intelligence to this IoT device. Using the artificial intelligence library TensorFlow, the artificial intelligence analyzes the camera's image data and displays the results on the monitoring screen. By applying these results to other fields, we can build a more efficient AIoT system. This system was programmed using a Raspberry Pi computer and Python, and TensorFlow, an artificial intelligence library, was also used in Python. The entire program utilized Node-Red, an IoT system building tool. In addition, a section was created to display the results of artificial intelligence on the monitoring screen. As a result, we successfully developed an AIoT system that can be applied to various fields.*

Keywords: *IoT, AIoT, data visualization, Raspberry Pi, TensorFlow, Node-Red.*

Introduction

Recently, the world has seen the emergence of new technologies in various fields due to the impact of the Fourth Industrial Revolution. The characteristics of Fourth Industrial Revolution technologies include technological, innovation, manufacturing innovation, platform-based technological innovation, and the Internet of Things, which connects the world as one through the internet. Moreover, there has been an ongoing effort to incorporate human intelligence into these technologies, making artificial intelligence a hot topic in recent times. Also, the core technologies of the 4th industrial revolution are cloud computing, artificial intelligence, virtual reality, and the Internet of Things. Many scientists are making great efforts to combine these technologies to create a more efficient system.

Among them, the fields of AI and IoT are the most representative and are of great interest in many countries, making them major research topics. In particular, efforts are being made to integrate these technologies to create new systems. In other words, research is being conducted to organically collaborate artificial intelligence and the Internet of Things to generate new synergies. The technology of adding artificial intelligence to IoT, represented by smart cities[1,2], smart factories[3,4], smart farms, and smart buildings[5,6], is a key focus for cities and local governments around the world.

These AIoT technologies are being applied in various fields, and many papers have been published. In particular, a paper was published on how AI meets the IoT field to create synergy effects [7]. In addition, a paper was published on how AIoT serves as a guide for architects [8]. Recently, AIoT has been applied to the sports field [9] and is being widely applied to the medical field [10,11,12].

This study implemented a basic AIoT system to spread AIoT technology to students.

First, the system was implemented using IoT technology, and then artificial intelligence functions were added to the developed system.

This system uses a Raspberry Pi computer and uses external sensors to measure external environmental conditions. The external sensors used are temperature and humidity sensors, image sensors (cameras), and ultrasonic sensors. Temperature, humidity, and distance can be measured. The external LED circuit is configured to allow external control from the monitor screen. The external LED circuit is configured to allow external control from the monitor screen.

The software used in this study basically used the Python language. Python was programmed using the Thonny Python tool provided by default by Raspberry Pi. Linux, which is used on Raspberry Pi computers, was used as the computer operating system. Node-Red Tool was used to control the Internet of Things system and also implemented a monitoring screen.

As a result, this study constructed an Internet of Things system including artificial intelligence. The results of the experiment conducted with the developed AIoT system were satisfactory after analysis by TensorFlow, and the collection of external environment data was also successful. In addition, the control of the LED for controlling external devices worked smoothly on the monitoring screen. This study was able to confirm the possibility of a new AIoT system by integrating artificial intelligence and the Internet of Things.

2. AIoT System (Theoretical Background)

2.1 Artificial Intelligence of Things (AIoT)

AIoT is an abbreviation for Artificial Intelligence of Things, and it means building a smarter, more efficient, and autonomous system by integrating artificial intelligence (AI) and the Internet of Things (IoT). In other words, AIoT technology is a technology that creates new synergy by adding artificial intelligence functions to the network, data collection, and monitoring screen configuration technology of the Internet of Things.

IoT (Internet of Things)

Things (IoT) can be defined as follows: It is a general technology that connects things to the Internet and collects and exchanges data through the Internet.

The Internet of Things can also be applied to the following fields: smart thermostats, wearable health trackers, surveillance cameras.

AI (Artificial Intelligence)

Artificial intelligence is a technology that allows computers to analyze data, learn from it, and make intelligent decisions. It is a computer that replaces human thinking. It is largely divided into machine learning and deep learning.

Benefits of AIoT

- Real-time decision-making
- Smart control and management of IoT devices
- Minimizing human intervention
- Improving the efficiency of related systems

In summary, AIoT collects data through devices connected to the IoT system, analyzes and learns using artificial intelligence functions, and gives intelligence to computers. It appropriately delivers the results to external devices or consumers using the IoT system. It can be said to be a technology that creates new effects by combining the two processes.

1.2 Basic configuration of AIoT system

The AIoT system is an integrated system of AI and IoT. The two separate fields are merged to create new synergies. It combines the data-collecting capabilities and connectivity of IoT devices with the data-processing capabilities of AI. The two technologies are highly complementary. In this study, the IoT system was first configured and the AIoT system was configured by adding artificial intelligence functions. Generally, the basic configuration of AIoT requires hardware and software. The hardware is the same as the IoT hardware system, and external sensors and external devices are connected to the system. In addition, the software requires a program that operates the IoT system. In addition, in order to add AI functions, an AI library must be added to the software.

In order for IoT and AI to merge and create synergy, the following process is required. Data received from the IoT system is stored in the computer database and analyzed and learned using artificial intelligence functions. The results determined by artificial intelligence are displayed on the monitoring screen, which is one of the IoT systems. In addition, screen design is also important so that users can easily understand the IoT monitoring screen.

This study was started to configure this system. We selected the main computer to be used in the AIoT system, decided on the types of sensors required for the system, and considered external devices. We also selected the computer language required to write software for operating the system. In addition, we searched for various AI libraries to add AI functions and selected the most efficient AI library.

3. Proposed AIoT system

3.1 Implemented system block diagram

Figure 1. AIoT System block diagram

The block diagram of the implemented AIoT system is shown in Figure 1. The proposed system can be divided into hardware and software parts. The hardware consists of the main computer Raspberry Pi 4, an internal device consisting of three sensors, and an external device consisting of two LEDs. The internal device is installed in the office, and the temperature measurement sensor and the distance measurement sensor can measure temperature, humidity, and distance, respectively. The software part is written in Python and consists of a program that controls each part or receives input from the sensor and outputs it to the monitoring screen, a monitoring screen program that identifies the situation, and a TensorFlow library that performs

AI functions.

Here is a detailed description of the proposed system: The computer receives the measurements from the sensor and analyzes the data. If an abnormality occurs, a warning light turns on on the computer. In addition, the computer can check the external environment changes through the monitoring screen and control external devices according to the situation. The computer analyzes and visualizes the received data, converts it into numbers and graphs that the user can easily understand, and displays the results on the monitor screen.

3.2 Used sensors

3.2.1 Sensor 1(DHT22)

(Temperature and humidity sensor)

Figure 2. Temperature and Humidity Sensor (DHT22)

Figure 2 shows the precision temperature and humidity sensor used in this study. The sensor consists of three wires: Vcc, GND, and DOUT. This sensor is widely used because it can measure precise temperature and humidity at a relatively low cost. In this study, DHT22 was selected for the design of the precision IoT system. Table 2 shows the specifications of DHT22. DHT22 is a precision temperature and humidity sensor that can measure temperature from -40°C to 80°C and humidity from 0% to 100%. The accuracy is $\pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ for temperature and $\pm 1\%$ for humidity. The detailed specifications of DHT22 are as shown in Table 1 below.

Table 1. DHT-22 (Temperature and humidity sensor)

Humidity measurement range	0-100% RH
Operating current	0.3mA (measuring) 60uA (standby)
Temperature measurement range	$-40-80^{\circ}\text{C}$
Accuracy	$\pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $\pm 1\%$
Operating voltage	3.5V~5V
Power Consumption	low power
number of pins	3 pins (Vcc, GND, DOUT)

3.2.2 Sensor 2 (HC-SR04)

(Ultrasonic distance sensor)

The sensor used in this paper is an ultrasonic distance sensor (HC-SR04), which is a generally inexpensive and easily available distance sensor. Figure 3 shows the ultrasonic distance sensor used in this study.

Figure 3. Ultrasonic Distance sensor(HC-SR04)

An ultrasonic sensor is a sensor that measures distance using ultrasonic waves. It measures distance using ultrasonic waves of a frequency band that humans cannot hear, and the transmission time of the ultrasonic waves. The frequency band of ultrasonic waves used is approximately 20 kHz to 200 kHz, which does not overlap with audible frequencies. An ultrasonic sensor consists of an ultrasonic generator and a receiver. The ultrasonic generator generates ultrasonic waves, and the receiver detects the reflection of the ultrasonic waves and measures the time. The distance is measured by calculating the reflection time between the ultrasonic generator and the receiver. Figure 3 shows the ultrasonic sensor used in this study. The ultrasonic sensor consists of two piezoelectric elements. The element marked T in the figure vibrates to send ultrasonic waves, and R detects the ultrasonic waves that are reflected and returned. The ultrasonic sensor uses four pins, and in addition to the power supply VCC and GND, it consists of a Trig pin to request detection start, and an Echo pin to calculate the distance.

Table 2. HC-SR04 (Ultrasonic distance sensor)

Operating voltage	5V
Quiescent current	< 2mA
Effectual angle	< 15°
Ranging distance	2 Cm ~ 500 Cm
Resolution	0.3 Cm

Table 2 shows the specifications of the ultrasonic sensor HC-SR04. HC-SR04 is a low-power device with an operating voltage of 5 V and a standby power of less than 2 mA. The effective measurement angle is 15 °, and the measurement distance is from 2 cm to 500 cm. The resolution is about 0.3 cm, and it is generally used as a distance measurement sensor.

3.2.3 Sensor 3 (C270) (Image sensor: Camera)

The sensor used in this study is a camera (C270), which is an image sensor. It is a sensor with a good resolution that is generally cheap and easily available. Figure 4 shows the camera, which is the image sensor used in this study.

Figure 4. Image sensor, Camera (C270)

The camera, which is the image sensor used in this study, is a Logitech C270 webcam. It is commonly used as an external camera for personal computers. The camera's video resolution is 720p, with a horizontal resolution of 1280 pixels and a vertical resolution of 720 pixels, or HD (high definition) resolution. In other words, this camera can shoot videos with a resolution of 720p. It uses widescreen HD 720p and has a built-in noise-cancelling microphone so that you can hear clearly even in noisy environments. It also has a screen brightness compensation device that brightens dark lighting.

3.2.4 External device (LED)

Figure 5. LED

Figure 6. LED Dimension

In this study, we included two external devices using LEDs. These devices were designed to control external devices from a screen monitor, and each device consisted of LEDs of different colors. The external devices could be controlled by turning the switch On and Off on the monitoring screen.

Figure 5 is a photograph of the LED used in this study. LED is a semiconductor device widely used throughout society. It is derived from the initials of 'Light Emitting Diode', and is a

semiconductor that emits light when current flows. It can directly convert electrical energy into light energy, so it has excellent energy efficiency and is widely used in display devices. LED is manufactured as a semiconductor with a PN junction structure. Since electronic energy is directly converted into light energy inside the PN junction, heat or kinetic energy is basically not needed to emit light, so it has excellent energy efficiency.

Electrons and holes injected from the electrode into the semiconductor recombine after passing through different energy bands across the electric field barrier near the PN junction. In the process of recombination, light energy is emitted. The size of the LED is as shown in Figure 6. The specifications of the LED used are as follows: Luminous intensity (20 mA): 40000 mcd, Forward voltage (20 mA): 3.1 V, 50% Output angle: 15 degrees.

3.3 Computer (Raspberry Pi 4)

Figure 7 shows the Raspberry Pi 4 used in this study. Raspberry Pi is a small computer that is used as a core in the IoT field.

Figure 7. Computer (Raspberry pi 4)

The Raspberry Pi 4 is a small single-board computer that can be configured as a complete computer by connecting a screen, keyboard, and mouse. The Raspberry Pi 4 used in this study has 8MB of RAM and uses the Linux-based Raspberry Pi OS as its operating system. It has two micro HDMI ports for connecting an external monitor, two USB 2.0 ports for using general external memory, and two high-speed USB 3.0 ports. It also has a jack for outputting external audio signals, a connector for connecting a dedicated display device, and a camera port for connecting a dedicated Raspberry Pi camera.

Raspberry Pi 4 has built-in Bluetooth and Wi-Fi, so you can transmit data wirelessly to the outside without connecting a separate communication device. The operating system used can be downloaded and installed from the Raspberry Pi website. The micro SD card used at this time can be 16GB or larger. If you use the Raspberry Pi imager provided on the website, you can easily install the operating system on the micro SD card.

Raspberry pi GPIO pins

Figure 8. Raspberry pi 4 pins map.

Figure 8 shows the GPIO and 40 pins of Raspberry Pi 4. The Raspberry Pi 4 has 40 external connection pins that can send and receive data from the outside. Each pin is numbered, and users can use these pins to connect to the outside. There are pins for power, ground, and special functions. Since all pins on the Raspberry Pi 4 use +3.3V as the operating power, you must always be careful when connecting them to other computers or external circuits. In this study, the PIR sensor was connected to GPIO pin 7. Python and C are mainly used to control external circuits, but in this study, the Python language was used for programming. The software editor used the “Thonny” editor built into the Raspberry Pi OS.

3.4 Software (Python and TensorFlow)

IoT Software

The software was basically structured using the Python language. The IoT program used the Node-Red tool. The Node-Red tool is a specialized tool for IoT and is used by many IoT engineers. The Node-Red tool was used to create a monitoring screen. IoT requires a screen that can monitor all external environments. This screen displays the data received from each sensor in numbers and graphs. To add artificial intelligence capabilities, a separate section was created on the monitoring screen to display the AI results.

AI software

The AI software used the TensorFlow library. TensorFlow is an AI library widely used by AI engineers and scientists. TensorFlow includes basic learning content, so users can easily use its functions. In this study, the judgment function of TensorFlow was used and included in the main program. The AI execution results are displayed on the AI program screen and displayed in the AI result section of the main monitoring screen.

4. Experiments

We conducted experiments using the completed system. The first experiment is a pure IoT system experiment without AI. Figure 9 shows the IoT software using Node-Red. Figure 10 shows the monitoring screen that can grasp all situations.

Figure 9. Software

Figure 10. Monitoring screen

Figure 11 shows the Raspberry Pi 4 used in the study. Figure 12 shows the entire AIoT hardware system. The camera is connected as an image sensor, DHT22 as a temperature and humidity sensor, and the ultrasonic sensor as a distance sensor.

Figure 11. Raspberry pi 4

Figure 12. AIoT system

Figures 13 and 14 show the appearance with AI features added. Figure 13 shows the picture taken by the camera and the result displayed on the TensorFlow screen. Figure 14 shows the monitoring screen with AI features. The AI software outputs the AI results, which are connected to the monitoring screen. All experiments performed with the implemented system have been confirmed to work normally.

Figure 13. AI TensorFlow program

Figure 14. Monitoring screen with AI

5. CONCLUSION

In this study, a basic IoT system for AIoT convergence field education was constructed. In order to include AI functions in the constructed IoT system, the TensorFlow library was used to add AI functions. The IoT system consists of hardware and software parts, and the experimental results showed that each part operated smoothly. The software was developed

using the Python language, and the Node-Red tool was used. A separate monitoring screen was also constructed. On the monitoring screen, changes in data received from the sensor could be checked numerically and graphically, and it was confirmed that ON/OFF control of the external circuit was also possible. In order to add AI functions to the IoT system, we added AI functions by including TensorFlow in the main program. Only TensorFlow can be executed, and the results of the executed AI are displayed on the monitoring screen. The AI program takes a picture with the camera and analyzes the captured image using TensorFlow. When the analysis is completed, the result is displayed on the AI screen and transmitted to the monitoring screen, and the same results can be confirmed on the monitoring screen. As a result, this study implemented an AIoT system that includes AI functions in the IoT system and confirmed that all systems were operating normally.

This study was conducted to collaborate between the Internet of Things and artificial intelligence. As a result, this study presents new possibilities in the field of AIoT research, which has not yet been studied much.

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